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LETTER Rotational Elastography: Six degree-of-freedom seismology in soft tissues measures local elasticity with diffuse fields

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dd Month yyyy 4Johannes Aichele¹ ¹ETH Zurich, Department of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Institute of Geophysics6 **E-mail:** johannes.aichele@rwth-aachen.de**Keywords:** Rotational Elastography | Magnetic resonance Elastography | Rotational Seismology | Elasticity
8 Tomography | Tissue characterisation | Shear wave imaging | Diffuse wave-field imaging | Phase-conjugation|
Interferometry**Abstract**

12 Elasticity is a key indicator for soft tissue pathologies such as malignant tumours. I show
13 theoretically and experimentally that leveraging the full six Degree-of-freedom shear wave
14 motion enables local elasticity for shear wave imaging with spatially diffuse fields. The
15 experimental proof-of-concept is presented for magnetic resonance elastography of a brain
16 phantom, but the theoretical derivation holds for various elastography imaging methods.
17 Inspired by rotational seismology, this work introduces new acquisition and processing
18 methods for non-invasive soft tissue characterisation using random wave-fields. A second
19 result combining rotational elastography with seismic interferometry illustrates the
20 method's potential to be combined with existing setups and processing techniques. Beyond
21 its application in Magnetic Resonance Imaging, an adaptation of rotational elastography
22 for ultrasound imaging and optical coherence tomography could be envisaged.

1 Introduction

24 Tissue elasticity has been probed throughout centuries by manual palpation to detect malignant
25 stiffness changes in soft tissues, with written evidence dating back to the Ebers papyrus of old
26 Egypt [1]. In elastography, the same principle is routinely applied for quantitative imaging.
27 Employing shear waves to 'palpate' tissue, shear wave elastography detects and quantifies liver
28 fibrosis and cirrhosis [2], as well as tumours in the liver, breast, prostate, pancreas, and brain [3].
29 Tissue elasticity is quantified by measuring shear wave induced displacements, typically through
30 travel time estimation [4], wave-number analysis of plane waves [3, 5], or inversion of the wave
31 equation [3, 6, 7]. The shear wave induced displacements can be measured with ultrasound, optical,
32 or magnetic resonance imaging [8, 9, 10, 11], and in 2D and 3D allow elasticity tomography. In the
33 present work, I propose a conceptually new way to estimate elasticity locally, based on the recent
34 development of six Degree-of-freedom seismology. Exploiting the local ratio of displacement and
35 rotation, my proof-of-concept allows retrieval of elasticity contrasts on the voxel scale for random
36 wave-fields in shear wave elastography.

Soft tissue elasticity is proportional to elastic wave speed, which represents the coefficient
38 relating the Laplacian and second-order time-derivatives in the homogeneous wave equation. Shear
39 wave elastography usually recovers wave speed either by directly solving the wave equation or by
40 solving solutions to the wave equation. To solve the wave equation, displacements need to be twice
41 differentiable in space to compute the Laplacian. However, second-order derivatives in space are
42 highly noise sensitive [12], and wave equation inversion is computationally expensive. The
43 alternative, solving solutions to the wave equation instead, usually requires coherent plane waves.
44 However, these are often difficult to achieve because scattering and noise sources in the body can
45 interfere with coherent waves and induce unwanted phase fluctuations [13]. The mitigation methods
46 commonly used are spatial averaging and directional frequency wavenumber filters [14], originally
47 proposed in seismic imaging [15, 16]. However, the first leads to loss of resolution, and the second
48 can introduce ringing and aliasing [17]. Thus, methods that can resolve shear wave speed in
complex, fluctuating fields that do not require a wave equation inversion offer clear advantages.

50 1.1 Rotational Seismology

To develop such a method, I propose to leverage an elastic wave property derived from seismology: The phase velocity of some seismic waves connects the rotation of particle velocity and the translational acceleration [18, 19], allowing wave speed estimation with a single point sensor.

This principle underlies rotational seismology and has recently enabled the retrieval of the local wave speed or site response for singular seismic stations and small dense arrays [20, 21, 19]. How can we retrieve wave speed with a single sensor and location? Conceptually, knowledge of the rotation vector adds three Degrees-of-freedom to the three translational motions, similar to knowing the wave vector \vec{k} . In fact, rotation and wave vector are intrinsically linked ([18], equations (4) and (5) of the SI), and expressions for seismic wave speeds, based solely on rotational and translational motion, have been derived by [18]. From the single station wave-speed retrieval, it follows directly that the rotational seismology principle also applies to diffuse fields, which are characterised by the presence of all directions of propagation and in the case of cavities also referred to as reverberant fields. As a consequence, rotational seismology has previously been applied to ambient noise seismology [21], where the background seismic field in the earth is exploited for imaging and monitoring.

Rotational motion can either be measured through rotational sensors [22], or derived from arrays of translational sensors through spatial gradients. Array derived rotations (ADR) are then computed at each sensor location via finite differences. In contrast to methods that invert the wave equation, only first spatial derivatives are required to retrieve wave speed when leveraging rotational and translational motion simultaneously with dense arrays. Compared to previous plane wave solutions such as time-of-flight and phase gradient algorithms, neither coherent waves, directional filters, spatial averaging, nor local homogeneity beyond the finite difference stencil of the first spatial derivatives (eq. 1 SI) is required in ADR.

74 2 Rotational elastography

To apply the rotational seismology principle to shear wave elastography, we can exploit array derived rotations for medical imaging. Elastography images represent a very dense array of virtual elastic wave sensors inside the body. In the seismology analogy, each pixel or voxel serves as a 'seismometer'. In ultrasonic time-domain methods this is done through speckle tracking, and in harmonic magnetic resonance elastography (MRE) via MRI sequences that use magnetic field gradients to encode shear wave induced motion. In soft tissues, the large wave speed contrast between compressional and shear waves of two orders of magnitude causes them to separate naturally in time and to exhibit distinct wavelengths. As a result, virtual sensors (MRI voxels) are well suited to measure shear wave motion. The key difference between seismology and elastography is that the virtual sensors in elastography are located in situ, where they can directly probe body waves. In contrast, seismometers are located at the earth's surface, where surface waves are the dominant wave type.

The principle of six Degree-of-freedom (six component) seismology can thus be applied to elastography by employing shear body waves for local elasticity measurements. The six components comprise, for each voxel, the 3D translational motion (i.e. displacement) and 3D rotational motion. For array derived rotations, the three components of translational motion need thus to be measured in all three spatial dimensions over time or frequency. Then, the particle velocity of plane shear body waves at the angular frequency ω and with wave vector k and their rotations can be expressed as:

$$\dot{u}_x = i\omega A \cos \theta \cos \varphi \sin(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \varphi), \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{u}_y = i\omega A \cos \theta \sin \varphi \sin(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \varphi), \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{u}_z = -i\omega A \sin \theta \sin(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \varphi), \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{\phi}_x = i\frac{\omega}{2} Ak \sin \varphi \cos(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \varphi), \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\phi}_y = -\frac{i\omega}{2} Ak \cos \varphi \cos(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \varphi), \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{\phi}_z = 0, \quad (6)$$

94 where θ is the angle from the wave's propagation direction to the z-axis, φ is the angle between the x-axis and the projection of the wave vector on the xy -plane, A is Amplitude, t is time, \mathbf{r} is the radial coordinate, \dot{u}_x is acceleration in x , $\dot{\phi}_y$ is the rotation of the y-component particle velocity, ω is the wave's angular frequency, k is the wavenumber, and \mathbf{k} is the wave vector. Since all three

98 components of particle velocity and rotation are measured, the polarisation and propagation
 direction, and thus ϕ and θ , can be resolved directly from the vector $\vec{u}_{x,y,z}$ (see eq. (1) - eq. (6) or
 100 [23]). Equation (4) and eq. (5) show that rotation depends directly on the wavenumber. Thus, by
 first solving for angles θ and ϕ , and consequently for the wave number k , the wave vector \mathbf{k} can be
 102 determined from the knowledge of the six-Degrees-of-Freedom of translational and rotational
 motion. Furthermore, it follows from eq. (1) - eq. (6), that dividing the time-derivative of a
 104 component of motion by a non-identical component of rotation allows solving for the in situ local
 phase velocity of a shear wave. Deriving eq. (1) in time, dividing by eq. (5) and rearranging we get:

$$c_s = \frac{\omega}{k} = \frac{(\ddot{u}_x/\dot{\phi}_y)}{-2i \cos(\theta)} \quad (7)$$

106 The above expression for translational and rotational motion is still in the time domain, most
 common in ultrasonic or optical elastography. However, 3-component measurements for these
 108 methods are still scarce. I limit the following experimental proof-of-concept thus to MRE, where
 the acquisition of three components of motion in 3D allows for the largest field of view and permits
 110 imaging beyond hard barriers, such as the skull. In MRE, shear wave excitation is often done
 harmonically, such that the Fourier amplitude $\mathcal{F}[u(t)] = \tilde{U}(\omega)$ at a specific frequency can be
 112 obtained for three independent directions of motion and in three dimensions. In the Fourier
 domain, time derivatives become multiplications by $i\omega$ and eq. (7) becomes thus for rotational
 114 magnetic resonance elastography (rMRE):

$$c_s = \frac{\omega}{k} = \frac{(i^2 \omega^2 \tilde{U}_x / i\omega \tilde{\Phi}_y)}{-2i \cos(\theta)} = \frac{(i\omega \tilde{U}_x / \tilde{\Phi}_y)}{-2 \cos(\theta)} \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\Phi}_y$ is the temporal Fourier transform of ϕ_y . An equivalent relation exists for $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$.
 116 Hence, any order of the kinematic motion field can be leveraged to calculate the shear wave speed
 for harmonic fields. If ω is known, the wave speed can be retrieved directly and, ignoring viscous
 118 and anisotropic effects, the linear elastic shear modulus is related to the wave speed by $c_s = \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}}$,
 where $\rho \approx 1000 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ in soft tissues and G is the shear modulus.

120 Thus, the only numerical requirement for rotational magnetic resonance elastography (rMRE)
 are the first spatial derivatives in x , y , and z , which are used to compute the rotational motions
 122 $\tilde{\Phi}_x$, $\tilde{\Phi}_y$, and $\tilde{\Phi}_z$ (eq. 1 SI). For finite differences, the numerical stencil should be much smaller than
 the wavelength. An intrinsically rotational point sensor does not have such a wavelength limit.
 124 Thus, directly measuring rotations with MRI sequences that encode rotations in the magnetic field
 gradients would be preferable, but the only direct rotation measurement with MRI known to the
 126 author is for granular flow [24], not wave propagation. The working principle of rotational
 elastography is sketched in fig. 1 for a single propagation angle of a plane shear wave.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the Rotational Elastography principle. The 2 black points represent 2 voxels inside the imaged MRI Volume, indicated by the black box. Each voxel is located in a region of different elasticity. Propagation of a plane shear wave is illustrated by the dashed red and blue parallel lines. At each voxel, complex displacement \tilde{U} and rotation $\tilde{\Phi}$ are measured. Their ratio $\frac{\tilde{\Phi}}{\tilde{U}}$ is proportional to the wave-number \vec{k} . Heterogeneous elasticity, and thus \vec{k} , is visualized by varying distance of dashed lines. Multiplying \tilde{U} by $i\omega$, which is equivalent to taking the time derivative in the time domain, allows retrieving the local wave speed.

128 2.1 Diffuse field dataset

I tested rotational elastography on experimental data acquired by Kabir et al. [25] (publicly available under a creative commons licence [26]). They acquired a MRE dataset of a brain mimicking phantom that consists of a homogeneous background and several stiffer inclusions. Kabir et al. give the inclusion diameters as 18, 12, and 4mm [25]. They also measured the phantom's background shear elasticity at 3.34 ± 0.04 kPa and the inclusions at 8.15 ± 0.05 kPa with an independent method. The authors used mechanical testing of cylindrical samples of the same gelatine batches as the background and inclusions [25] to validate elasticity independent of elastography. They excited shear waves at 70 Hz to create a reverberant field, which is a spatially diffuse field. Instead of a single propagation angle, many, ideally all, propagation angles are present.

Such diffuse fields can either be created through distributed sources, such as mechanical actuators and natural sources inside the body, or boundary reflections, reverberations, and wave scattering. Historically, these fields have been considered as noise in acoustic and elastic imaging methods and have either been filtered for individual propagation angles or avoided altogether by creating a coherent wave-field with a dominant wave propagation angle. However, in recent decades diffuse fields have been leveraged through interferometry, such as ambient noise cross-correlation and time-reversal methods in seismology [27, 28], acoustics [29, 30], and elastography [31, 32, 13, 33, 34, 35].

Spatially diffuse fields are ideal for rotational seismology, as the presence of multiple angles of propagation increases each voxel's exposure to shear waves at a high Signal-to-Noise-Ratio. The wave-field diffusivity can be rooted in distributed noise sources as well as scattering and reverberations. Because rotational elastography is based on local amplitudes of motion (displacement and rotation), and not the phase of the wave, a good illumination is required, but spatial phase coherency is not.

The dataset of Kabir et al. [26] is particular suited to test rotational elastography because the authors measured all three components of motion in 3D. Furthermore, they report the elasticity reference values from mechanical testing as well as the elastography results using two existing methods in [25].

156 2.2 Experimental results

To prepare the motion data for rotational elastography, I apply the processing outlined in the SI on the X -, Y -, Z -Motion retrieved by Kabir et al. [25]. The real parts of the translational (top) and rotational (bottom) motion fields for $x - y$ -slice 24 are displayed in fig. 2. The normalised amplitudes show that the field is not equipartitioned, with the weakest rotations in $\Re(\tilde{\Phi}_z)$, indicating preferential shear wave polarisation. An exception is the boundary of the large inclusion. There, higher z -rotation amplitudes are observed, likely as a result of scattering at the inclusion.

Figure 2: Normalized real part of the motion Fields as provided by . Top: Translational Motions from Kabir et al. [25]; Bottom: Rotational Motions, derived via a 1 voxel central finite difference stencil)

Inside the inclusions, $\Re(\tilde{\Phi}_x)$ shows the highest amplitudes, while the background amplitudes are highest for $\Re(\tilde{\Phi}_x)$. Furthermore, the y -rotations ($\tilde{\Phi}_y$) in fig. 2 show that the two large inclusions seem to shadow the outer part ($x \approx 13$ cm) of the phantom. The wave-field is thus not perfectly diffuse. Such uneven exposure to propagation directions across the phantom can be expected due to the use of a single mechanical driver [25], but the existing reverberations should suffice for the proof-of-concept. Rotational elastography (eq. (8)) in the Fourier domain using $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ results in the elasticity map shown in the first panel (top left) of fig. 3. It represents a central $x - y$ -slice (Nr. 24 of 40). The two larger inclusions are well-defined, with elasticities above 7 kPa. The background is well distinguished, with elasticity values below 4 kPa. Variations in background elasticity and semicircular shapes of increased elasticity suggest an imprint of wave-field focusing effects on the tomography. Indeed, if the wave-field is not perfectly diffuse, the SNR will vary in space. Furthermore, an elasticity measurement based purely on shear body waves (eq. (8)) might break down on a free surface or rigid boundary. Here, a local adaptation of the algorithm to account for surface waves and S-P conversions might be required. Such equations can be developed, as was shown for the seismological case by [18]. The second panel (top middle) shows the results for using $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$ instead of $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$. The observations from fig. 2 are confirmed. Illumination by $\tilde{\Phi}_y$ -polarized shear waves is better in the background, while $\tilde{\Phi}_x$ -polarization illumination is better in the inclusions, resulting in a smoother background in panel 2 than in panel 1. Since different polarizations contain different artefacts, it stands to reason to combine them. Panel 3 (top right) shows the elasticity tomography after averaging the shear wave speeds retrieved with $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ and $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$.

It should be noted that the subzone elastography [36] and the reverberant elastography results of Kabir et al. in the original study [25] also show a non-homogeneous background and artefacts. To compare fig. 3 with subzone and reverberant elastography results, please see Figure 4f and 4g of [25], an open-access publication.

2.3 Interferometry & rotational elastography

The background elasticity estimation with rotational elastography can be further improved by exploiting the diffusivity of the reverberant field through wave-field interferometry. In wave-field interferometry, numerical time-reversal (cross-correlation) of diffuse fields leads to Green's function retrieval between sensors [37]. For example, the focal spot time reversal method of [31, 38],

numerically creates coherent, focusing wave-fields from diffuse wave-fields, thus turning a noisy
 194 signal into a coherent signal on a dense array. Note that the wave-field diffusivity is a requirement,
 and thus the more diffuse the field, the better the interferometric wave-field reconstruction [39]. By
 196 adapting time domain interferometry to harmonic fields, we can create a multitude of
 phase-conjugated wave-fields, which are the harmonic equivalent of the time-reversed focusing
 198 fields. Therefore, the complex value $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}$ of the 3 measured components of motion in a voxel is
 multiplied by the complex conjugate of the wave-field for each component in a 3D window:
 200 $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)^{PC} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{r}_0)\tilde{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{r})^*$. This phase conjugation is the harmonic equivalent to cross-correlation
 in the time domain. For any $\mathbf{r}_0 \in \mathbf{r}$, where \mathbf{r} are the voxels in the field of view of MRE, a phase
 202 conjugated wave-field $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)^{PC}$ is thus created. Rotational elastography processing on each of
 these wave-fields then gives an average shear wave speed:

$$c_s(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{r_0=1}^N \frac{i\omega\tilde{U}_x^{PC}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)/\tilde{\Phi}_y^{PC}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)}{-2\cos(\theta)}, \quad (9)$$

204 where N is the number of voxels \mathbf{r} . Large N will thus include Green's functions between distant
 voxels $r_0 - r$ in the average, while smaller N focus on short distance Green's functions. The second
 206 and third rows of fig. 3 show the results of applying rotational elastography after 3D phase
 conjugation with two window sizes. Both interferometry window sizes result in a reduction of
 208 boundary effects and wave-field imprints compared to the pure rotational processing. The
 background is thus retrieved more homogeneously. Furthermore, using $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$ (panel 5) instead of
 210 $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ further reduces boundary effects. The improvements over pure rotational elastography are
 likely because 3D phase conjugation attenuates wave types that do not illuminate the entire 3D
 212 region-of-interest. Thus, body shear waves are dominant after interferometry, while the spatially
 limited guided and surface waves are attenuated or suppressed during phase conjugation. The fact
 214 that using $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$ suppresses boundary effects better than using $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ suggests that $\tilde{\Phi}_x$ is the
 dominant polarisation of surface waves.

216 The 3D phase conjugation of eq. (9) creates multiple (N) coherent fields in the imaging space
 from a single diffuse field, effectively increasing the signal that contributes to eq. (8). Thus, the
 218 larger the window size, the smoother the background. This is confirmed by a comparison of the
 lower row (win=15) and middle row (win=5) in fig. 3. However, large windows have a drawback.
 220 If multiple wave types are present, interferometry between a voxel dominated by, for example, a
 surface wave and a voxel dominated by a shear wave will be incoherent. Only interferometry
 222 between the same wave type will reconstruct a coherent wave. For large windows, incoherent
 contributions to eq. (9) from body wave dominated voxels \mathbf{r} will dominate for surface wave
 224 dominated voxels \mathbf{r}_0 . Hence, a small window is more adapted near the boundaries because it
 remains within the penetration depth of surface waves, such that the same wave type dominates
 226 both \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{r}_0 . Similarly, large windows risk to smooth out the inclusion, which might locally
 create multi-wave type fields via scattering. However, in a homogeneous background, where body
 228 waves will dominate, the large window results in a smoother background retrieval.

The phase conjugation results of Panel 5 and 8 also confirm the bad illumination by $\tilde{\Phi}_y$ already
 230 observed in fig. 2 $\tilde{\Phi}_y$. The region around $x \approx 13$ cm; $y \approx 10$ cm provides little coherent signal, even
 after phase conjugation, resulting in the visible dark region in panels 5 and 8.

232 Furthermore, the right-hand inclusion's elasticity is also lower for larger windows than for
 smaller windows. This could be due to the aforementioned shadowing and inferior field diffusivity
 234 in this part of the imaging volume, which would deteriorate the quality of interferometry, as has
 been shown previously in seismology [40, 41] and elastography [31].

236 For panels 6 and 9 of fig. 3, $\tilde{U}_y, \tilde{\Phi}_x$ and $\tilde{U}_x, \tilde{\Phi}_y$ are combined to retrieve c_s as the average of
 both polarizations, in the same way as for panel 3 in fig. 3:

$$c_s(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2N} \left(\sum_{r_0=1}^N \frac{i\omega\tilde{U}_x^{PC}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)/\tilde{\Phi}_y^{PC}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)}{-2\cos(\theta)} + \sum_{r_0=1}^N \frac{i\omega\tilde{U}_y^{PC}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)/\tilde{\Phi}_x^{PC}(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_0)}{2\cos(\theta)} \right) \quad (10)$$

238 The result shows again a compromise between background and inclusion elasticity retrieval.

240 Finally, panels 4 and 6 show a small stiff region of the approximate size of the 4 mm inclusion
 (white circular marker in fig. 3. It is located where we would suspect the smallest inclusion, which
 in previous studies remained invisible to MRI and MRE [25]. Pure rotational elastography without
 242 interferometry also shows this stiff region, but it is difficult to distinguish it from artefacts. With
 large window interferometry (bottom row), it disappears, likely because it is exposed primarily to

244 surface waves. While large window phase conjugation between different wave types results in
 245 cross-terms that cancel out, small window phase conjugation implies that surface waves motions in
 246 \mathbf{r}_0 are multiplied with phase conjugated surface waves in \mathbf{r} , which reconstructs a coherent surface
 247 wave field. Note that applying eq. (8) or eq. (9) to surface waves might contain a systematic error
 248 in the elasticity estimation, because these equations are strictly valid only for shear body or plane
 Love waves. However, this simple body wave model has previously been successfully applied to
 249 surface waves in seismology [42], where, in the case of unknown wave type, it is accordingly named
 250 apparent shear wave speed. Here, this apparent shear wave speed detects a stiff inclusion of
 251 $\approx 0.1\lambda_s$ (shear wavelength) that remained undetected in MRI and MRE images [25], corroborating
 252 the applicability of eq. (7) and eq. (8) to sub-wavelength heterogeneity imaging in elastography,
 253 analogous to their established use in seismology.

Figure 3: Shear modulus tomography through Rotational Elastography eq. (8) of the experimental brain phantom data of [26] at 70 Hz, visualized in fig. 2. A slice in $x - y$ is shown. Top: Rotational elastography using different polarizations $\tilde{U}_{x/y}$ and $\tilde{\Phi}_{y/x}$. The third panel is the average of the first two. Middle: Interferometric processing in 3D through Phase conjugation eq. (9) and subsequent rotational elastography on the same polarizations as above, with a phase conjugation in a 5 voxel 3D window. Bottom: Same as above with phase conjugation in a 15 voxel 3D window. The diameter of the three stiff inclusions is given as 18, 12 and 4 mm by [25]. The smallest inclusion is invisible in MRI, subzone, and reverberant elastography [25]. Nominal background elasticity is 3.34 ± 0.04 kPa and inclusion elasticity is 8.15 ± 0.05 kPa [25]. The insert sketches the slice orientation in a phantom, and the indicated translational and rotational motion vectors illustrate that each voxel/pixel is the result of leveraging six degrees-of-freedom.

3 Image Characterisation & Noise analysis

256 To confirm the visual results presented above, the results are analysed quantitatively and with
257 respect to noise in the following. fig. 4 top left shows three manually drawn Regions-Of-Interest
258 (ROI) with diameters 18.1 mm, 11.8 mm, 0.56 mm for the stiff inclusions and three manually
259 drawn background ROIs of approximately the same radius. The bottom table reports mean values,
260 standard deviations and Signal-to-Noise-Ratios (SNR) for each ROI, as well as
261 Contrast-to-Noise-Ratio (CNR) values for each inclusion-background pair. The mean inclusion
262 stiffness error is consistently below 5%, while in the background it reaches maximum 22%. Different
263 methods for calculating CNR (standard CNR, CNR_{dB} , gCNR), reported in fig. 4 bottom, are
264 consistently above detection thresholds, with the lowest CNR being 11.7 for the largest inclusion.
265 The Edge-Spread-Function (ESF) [43] between each inclusion and the associated background ROI
266 shows that inclusion size estimation is feasible with rotational elastography. For the two large
267 inclusions, the 25% crossings of the ESF coincide with the radius of the inclusion within 5% and
268 10%. The smallest inclusion is overestimated, and there, the 75% crossing is closer to the true
269 radius. This confirms the small-scale heterogeneity imaging results of [44, 45] in seismology for
270 rotational elastography. They showed that the wave speed contrast between small heterogeneities
271 and the background affects rotations strongly even for small heterogeneity size to wavelength
272 ratios. In contrast, translational wavefield measurements sense a smoothed effective medium. Small
273 inclusions become therefore detectable with rotations, but a correction factor may be required to
274 estimate their size accurately (see [45] for correction tensors in rotational seismology).

275 The Octahedral-Shear-Strain-Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (OSS-SNR) [46] of the motion data were
276 reported as 51 by [25]. To evaluate how diffuse field rotational elastography performs in the
277 presence of noise, I added 50 % additive white Gaussian noise to the phantom mask, such that the
278 ratio of the noise standard deviation (σ_n) to the signal Root-Mean-Square (RMS) is 0.5. The noise
279 is split equally between the real and imaginary parts of the motion data displayed in 2, such that
280 $\mathbb{E}[|n|^2] = \sigma_n^2$. The full motion fields with added noise and the elasticity maps generated from the
281 motion fields with added noise equivalent to fig. 3 are displayed in the Supplementary material.
282 Here, the elasticity map from the noise containing field equivalent to fig. 3 panel 7 is shown in the
283 top right panel of fig. 4. Although the background is visibly less homogeneous than fig. 3 panel 7,
284 both maps are remarkably comparable. The noise metrics equivalent to fig. 4 bottom for all 9
285 noise-free tomographies and all 9 perturbed tomographies are reported in the Supplementary
286 material.

ROI	Noise (std %)	PC win	G (kPa)	SNR	CNR	CNR _{dB} (dB)	gCNR	ESF ₂₅ (cm)	ESF ₇₅ (cm)
INC 1	–	–	8.2 ± 3.5	2.3	11.7	13.6	0.98	0.94	0.62
BG 1	–	–	2.7 ± 0.47	5.8	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	–	–	7.9 ± 2.1	3.7	40.9	21.4	1.0	0.66	0.44
BG 2	–	–	2.7 ± 0.13	21.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	–	–	7.8 ± 1.1	7.4	42.7	33.4	1.0	0.46	0.22
BG 3	–	–	2.6 ± 0.12	22.0	–	–	–	–	–
INC 1	50	15	5.3 ± 0.78	6.8	7.6	25.9	0.98	1.4	0.84
BG 1	50	15	2.6 ± 0.35	7.5	–	–	–	–	–
INC 2	50	15	3.0 ± 0.33	9.0	39.3	23.7	0.97	0.76	0.45
BG 2	50	15	2.1 ± 0.02	87.9	–	–	–	–	–
INC 3	50	15	3.6 ± 0.44	8.3	73.4	28.2	0.88	0.56	0.20
BG 3	50	15	2.1 ± 0.02	96.9	–	–	–	–	–

Figure 4: Top left: Lesion and background regions manually identified are displayed on the modulus map of fig. 3 panel 1. The 18 and 12 mm lesions are known from [25]. The 4 mm is guessed from the rMRE data, because it is neither visible in MRI, nor previous MRE results in [25]. Top right: Additive white Gaussian noise is generated to the phantom mask where the ratio of the noise standard deviation (σ_n) to the signal RMS is 0.5 (50% RMS). The noise is split equally between real and imaginary parts of the motion data displayed in 2 such that $\mathbb{E}[|n|^2] = \sigma_n^2$. Then the same processing as for panel 9 in fig. 3 is applied to retrieve the modulus map. Perturbed motion fields and rMRE results for the other components similar to fig. 3 can be found in the Supplementary material. Bottom: Quantitative values per ROI for the top row figures. CNR - Contrast-to-Noise ratio: $\text{CNR} = \frac{|\mu_{\text{INC}} - \mu_{\text{BG}}|}{\sigma_{\text{BG}}}$; $\text{CNR}_{\text{dB}} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{2(\mu_{\text{bg}} - \mu_{\text{ROI}})^2}{\sigma_{\text{ROI}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{bg}}^2} \right)$ as in [47]; gCNR - generalized GNR computed as in [48], ranges from 0 to 1. SNR - $\text{SNR} = \frac{\mu_{\text{ROI}}}{\sigma_{\text{bg}}}$. $\text{ESF}_{25/75}$. The 25%/75% crossings of the Edge Spread function ([43]) of the indicated normalized profiles connecting inclusion and background ROI centers using linear distance interpolation along the profile voxels.

4 Practical considerations

288 In order to exploit the full potential of rotational elastography beyond the present proof-of-concept,
289 two steps are crucial. Firstly, the experimental setup should ensure the best illumination possible
290 by creating a diffuse field that is equipartitioned between all propagation directions. This is
291 preferable to post-processing methods that equipartition the field, which is common practice in
292 seismology, where the experimental conditions cannot be modified. Secondly, the information
293 contained in 6C measures has not yet been fully leveraged in the current proof-of-concept. 6C
294 measures further allow for wave-type fingerprinting [18]. An adaptation from seismology to
295 elastography for fingerprinting should enable defining the locally dominant wave type at each voxel,
296 and, potentially allow for wavefield separation. Then, window sizes for interferometry can be
297 optimised, and analytic wave speed expressions for different wave types, similar to eq. (8), can be
298 derived and applied locally. However, even without fingerprinting, surface waves can be leveraged
299 with interferometry, as shown above. Therefore, interferometric processing should employ a window
300 size on the order of half the characteristic wavelength, since the majority of surface wave energy is
301 concentrated within this distance from the free surface. Note that applying the apparent shear wave
302 speed to a Rayleigh wave field will introduce a small systematic error. Although the principle of
303 retrieving phase velocity through the ratio of translational and rotational motion holds, the correct
304 expression for Rayleigh wave speed will differ by a factor from the expression for shear wave speed.

For noisy datasets, the present pilot study shows that interferometry is the first method of
305 choice. Secondly, noise can get boosted in the FD-stencil. Alternatively to the central 1 voxel FD
306 stencil employed here, higher orders of finite difference or inversion based spatial derivative
307 calculations can be used [49]. For the present noise-free dataset neither alternative derivative
308 method improved the reconstructions, indicating that for high quality datasets central FD stencils
309 are sufficient. Compared to coherent field MRE, diffuse field rotational elastography has two
310 inherent advantages with respect to wave attenuation. First, it is mitigated by interferometry,
311 which, as shown in fig. 4 bottom, results in significantly higher SNR values, even if white noise is
312 added to the motion data. Second, it relaxes the experimental constraints, which facilitates
313 achieving sufficient illumination throughout the sample.

5 Conclusion & Outlook

316 Figure 3 is the experimental proof-of-concept for quantitative elasticity imaging via rotational
317 elastography with harmonic wave fields. The method could enable the retrieval of sharp elasticity
318 contrasts in vivo to aid the detection and characterisation of small tumours or aggregopathies with
319 diffuse fields. This is especially relevant in organs where attenuation, scattering, and mode
320 conversions make the creation of coherent wave-fields challenging. For example, the reflective cavity
321 of the skull complicates coherent wave propagation in the brain. The present proof-of-concept is
322 based on the most basic expressions for body shear waves. Achieving the method's full potential
323 will require extending it to guided and surface waves. Future work should integrate polarisation
324 analysis [18] into rotation calculation, which will allow imaging of elasticity anisotropy.
325 Furthermore, viscoelasticity can be resolved by combining rotational elastography with
326 multi-frequency acquisitions or broadband MRE, an active research topic [50]. Broadband and
327 multi-frequency rotational elastography would allow for dispersion curve retrieval and thus
328 visco-elastic and poro-elastic characterisation, which more accurately describes stiffness of tissues
329 such as muscles [51], brain [52, 53], liver [2, 54] and lung [55, 56]. Lastly, rotational elastography
330 does not need to be limited to MRI or the frequency domain. Time-domain expressions already
331 exist, and the continuing development of 3D methods in ultrasound and 3-component measures in
332 optics could hold the potential to extend rotational elastography to ultrasound elastography and
333 optical coherence tomography. For surface waves such as Love and Rayleigh waves, particle motion
334 is restricted to a single plane such that even 4C measures could be used for rotational elastography,
335 for example, in the cornea. In ultrasound, the major challenge will be that the lateral dimension is
336 usually much less sensitive to tissue displacement than the axial dimension. US rotational
337 elastography might thus require multitransducer acquisitions [57] or improved beamforming
338 methods such as adaptive beamforming [57], matrix imaging [58, 59] or seismic imaging inspired
339 migration [60, 61, 62]. Furthermore, because rotational elastography obviates the need for
340 controlled shear-wave excitation, it can be implemented with any external mechanical shaker. This
341 allows for larger displacement amplitudes than acoustic radiation force impulse (ARFI-SWE)
342 imaging, which imposes stronger safety limits.

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